

Effects of Cherenkov radiation on the detection chains

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1. Nature of the Cherenkov effect

Cherenkov radiation is the optical shock wave produced by a charged particle moving through a dielectric medium at a velocity (v) exceeding the local phase velocity of light, c/n (n = refractive index). The minimum kinetic energy required for the effect is thus

$$E_{\min} = m_0 c^2 [(1 - n^{-2})^{-\frac{1}{2}} - 1] \quad (1)$$

with m_0 = rest mass. This threshold energy is shown in Table 1 for a medium with $n = 1.5$. From Figure 6.1.4.5 in the System Requirements it appears that only electrons are important (α particles are about 15 times fewer than protons in cosmic rays).

The light emission is highly directive, making an angle

$$\vartheta = \arccos(c/nv) \quad (2)$$

with the direction of travel (Figure 1). For $n = 1.5$ we have $0 \leq \vartheta < \arccos(1/n) \approx 48^\circ$. The wavefront is a cone with apex half-angle equal to $90^\circ - \vartheta$. Table 2 shows the emission angle as function of the energy ratio $E/E_{\min}$. Since the particles have a wide distribution of energies, it is clear that the angle is usually of the order of $40 - 45^\circ$ whenever the effect occurs at all.

The rate of photon production per unit wavelength is

$$\frac{dN}{d\lambda} = 2\pi \alpha Z^2 \sin^2 \vartheta s \lambda^{-2} \quad (3)$$

where $\alpha = 1/137$, Z is the particle charge (-1 for electrons), and s the length of the particle path over which the emission takes place. The factor λ^{-2} means that the radiation is particularly intense in the ultraviolet (UV) region of the spectrum. In many materials this UV radiation will cause phosphorescence in addition to the Cherenkov radiation. The phosphorescence occurs mostly in the red part of the spectrum and is delayed by up to some 100 μ s compared to the primary effect.

TABLE 1. Threshold energy for the Cherenkov effect in glass or quartz ($n = 1.5$) for the most abundant cosmic ray particles.

particle	$E_{\min}$
electron	0.17 MeV
proton	320 MeV
α (He^{2+})	1280 MeV

TABLE 2. Emission angle as function of relative particle energy ($n = 1.5$).

$E/E_{\min}$	θ
1	0
1.2	19°
2	34°
5	44°
10	47°
∞	48°

FIGURE 1. Geometry of the Cherenkov light wave front emitted by a relativistic particle (Ref. 1). $\beta = v/c$.

2. Effects on detector and detection electronics

The number of photoelectrons produced by the Cherenkov radiation from a single cosmic ray particle can be written, by integration of (3),

$$N = 2\pi \alpha Z^2 \sin^2\vartheta f s \int Q(\lambda) \lambda^{-2} d\lambda \quad (4)$$

where we have introduced $Q = (\text{optical transmittance}) \times (\text{quantum efficiency})$ and $f = \text{geometrical coupling factor between the dielectric and the photocathode}$. With $Z = -1$ and $\vartheta \approx 40^\circ$, we have approximately

$$N \approx 0.02 Q_0 f s \left(\lambda_{\min}^{-1} - \lambda_{\max}^{-1} \right) \quad (5)$$

where Q_0 is the maximum value of Q and $\lambda_{\min}$, $\lambda_{\max}$ the approximate (half- Q) wavelength limits.

It can be noted that N depends rather critically on the short-wavelength cut-off ($\lambda_{\min}$), i.e. whether quartz optics ($\lambda_{\min} \approx 150$ nm) or glass ($\lambda_{\min} \approx 350$ nm) is being used. With $\lambda_{\max} \approx 600$ nm, the ratio $N_{\text{quartz}}/N_{\text{glass}} \approx 3$. Actually, this ratio may be even higher, since the energy of a single UV photon may be sufficient to produce two photoelectrons.

According to (5), a single cosmic ray particle may produce a shower of several tens of photoelectrons within a fraction of a nanosecond. At the anode end of the detector, these are multiplied to a 'giant pulse', with amplitude several times that of 'normal' pulses (from single photoelectrons). The preamplifier and discriminator (PAD) contains an upper-level discriminator, which inhibits any output pulse if the amplitude of the input pulse exceeds a certain level. In principle, therefore, the giant pulses should not be counted, but the detector electronics is still 'busy' for about 25 ns after each giant pulse.

The giant pulses may also momentarily change the potentials of the dynodes and hence the multiplication factor, due to loading of the resistor chain. Depending on the time constant for recharging the dynodes, the pulse height distribution (and hence the quantum efficiency) may be slightly different for a short period after each Cherenkov pulse. Indirect effects of this and similar kind are not further considered here.

As for the net effect of the Cherenkov flash, we may distinguish three cases depending on the number of photoelectrons produced per cosmic ray particle:

- I. If $N \lesssim 1$, no giant pulse will occur and the electronics will count the Cherenkov pulses exactly as any uniform background illumination or dark count rate; that is, they go into the dark count budget. The reason for this is that (i) the Cherenkov flashes occur randomly (Poisson distributed) and (ii) each flash produces at most a single photoelectron.
- II. If $N \sim 10$, we get a giant pulse for each Cherenkov particle. In principle, giant pulses are not counted but produce additional 'dead time' which effectively reduces the sensitivity of the detection chain. It is difficult to estimate how many of these pulses are acceptable without more details about the electronics and pulse height distributions.
- III. If $N \gg 10$, we get not only a giant pulse, but probably also other adverse effects: 'daughter pulses' from phosphorescence, dynode loading, etc. Especially daughter pulses may be very harmful, as the resulting count distribution is non-Poissonian and might even be mistaken for a slit transit in the Star Mapper record. Daughter pulses follow within about 0.1 ms of the giant pulse, that is usually in the same sample interval, and are not eliminated by the PAD (as they are mostly produced by single photoelectrons). The importance of phosphorescence depends entirely on the materials used in detector windows and optical parts close to the photocathode.

3. Estimation of N for the Star Mapper optics

The most serious difficulty in applying (5) is to estimate the geometrical factor f . This is the fraction of Cherenkov photons actually reaching the photocathode, disregarding transmission losses (which are included in Q_0). In some cases the geometry in Figure 2 may be useful. Emission comes from a piece of glass at the distance d from the photocathode. The circumference of the light cone is $2\pi d \sin \theta$. If the photocathode diameter is $D > s \sin \theta$

FIGURE 2. Geometry of light reception from an optical element at distance d from the receptor (photocathode or lens).

FIGURE 3. Star Mapper relay lenses (= Figure 3.4.3 (2/2) in Ref. 2)

we find

$$f \approx D/(2\pi d \sin \Theta) \approx 0.25 D/d \quad (6)$$

The same formula can be used if we replace the photocathode with a lens, in which case d is the distance of the light emitting element to the lens. This supposes that all light originating in the element and captured by the next lens is actually transferred to the detector; this is usually the case in unvignetted systems.

For the PMT window we may assume $f \approx 0.5$. The resulting estimates are given in Table 3. They are admittedly very coarse but perhaps sufficient to see which of the cases I, II, or III applies to each element.

TABLE 3. Estimates of N for the different optical elements of the Star Mapper chain (refer to Figure 3 for assumed layout and dimensions).

element	$\lambda_{\min} - \lambda_{\max}$ [nm]	Q_o	s [mm]	D/d [mm]	f	N	case
PMT window	150 - 550	0.2	3	-	0.5	30	III
3rd lens	250 - 550	0.2	10	20/20	0.25	22	III
blocking filter	300 - 550	0.2	10	24/25	0.25	15	II - III
dichroic	BT 300 - 500	0.2	10	24/80	0.08	4	I - II
	VT 500 - 600	0.2	10	24/80	0.08	1.1	I
2nd lens	BT 350 - 500	0.15	10	24/140	0.04	1.0	I
	VT 500 - 600	0.15	10	24/140	0.04	0.4	I
1st lens	BT 350 - 500	0.15	10	29/135	0.05	1.3	I
	VT 500 - 600	0.15	10	29/135	0.05	0.5	I
grid	BT 350 - 500	0.15	10	29/90	0.08	2	I
	VT 500 - 600	0.15	10	29/90	0.08	0.8	I

To summarize the results for the SM relay optics:

- A. Electrons hitting the PMT windows, 3rd lenses, blocking filters, and possibly the dichroic will produce giant pulses. Depending on the materials, daughter pulses are also likely due phosphorescence. The rate of SM counts contaminated by multiple daughter pulses must be kept very low, probably of the order of 1 Hz, in order not to disturb significantly the SM transit determinations. Consequently, the inner parts of the SM relay optics + detectors should be shielded in such a way that only ~ 1 electron per second penetrates with $E > 0.17$ MeV.
- B. Each electron (with $E > 0.17$ MeV) hitting the grid, 1st lens, or 2nd lens will produce a 'normal' PMT pulse, indistinguishable from other background light sources. The acceptable rate of such hits may therefore be of the order of 10 Hz. In terms of shielding, however, this requirement is not much different from A.

It should be noted that the glass tube of the PMT's could act as light guides for Cherenkov radiation produced far from the photocathode, and that the shielding should therefore not be restricted to the front end. Concerning the grid, it may be possible to stop much of the light emission if the detector side of the grid could be made opaque, except in some slots around the slit groups.

4. Estimation of N for the primary detector

The IFOV is so small that the geometrical coupling factor is generally quite small, even for Cherenkov radiation produced in the detector window itself. In the most unfavourable situation of a normal impact on the IFOV centre, we have $f = 1$ for $s = D/(2 \tan \vartheta)$, where D in this case is the IFOV diameter (0.11 mm). Therefore, in (4), we have

$$\sin^2 \vartheta f s \leq 0.25 D \quad (7)$$

(for $\vartheta \leq 48^\circ$), and with $Q_0 = 0.1$, $\lambda_{\min} = 150$ nm, and $\lambda_{\max} = 600$ nm, we find $N \approx 0.6$. (We disregard the effects of the particle impact on the photocathode. Surely this will produce a giant pulse?) However, the probability of this is of the order of $(D/25 \text{ mm})^2 \approx 2 \cdot 10^{-5}$ compared with other hits on the IDT front surface.

For the IDT relay optics, we can use a geometric argument similar to Figure 2, but for $D \ll s$, to deduce that $\sin^2 \theta f s \approx D^2 / (8d)$; hence

$$N \approx 0.006 Q_0 D^2 d^{-1} (\lambda_{\min}^{-1} - \lambda_{\max}^{-1}) \quad (8)$$

With $d = 0.06$ m, 350-600 nm, $Q_0 = 0.1$, and $D = 1.1 \cdot 10^{-4}$ m, we find $N \approx 1.5 \cdot 10^{-4}$.

Finally for the grid, we obtain by means of (6) $f \approx 0.07$ from the grid to the first relay lens, and then another factor $\approx (0.11 \text{ mm} / 14 \text{ mm})^2 \approx 6 \cdot 10^{-5}$ for the IFOV-to-field ratio; hence the effective $f \approx 4 \cdot 10^{-6}$ and $N \approx 1.0 \cdot 10^{-4}$.

To summarize the results for the primary detector, it seems that giant pulses are possibly produced only by direct particle hits on the IFOV area, whereas other impacts result in a single photoelectron with probability $\sim 10^{-4}$ to 10^{-3} . If a contribution of 1 Hz to the dark counts is accepted, then not more than ~ 1000 electrons/s (with $E > 0.17$ MeV) are allowed to hit the IDT, relay optics, or grid.

5. Shielding efficiency

The shielding of e.g. aluminium against relativistic electrons is due to ionization and bremsstrahlung, converting the kinetic energy of the particle to heat and X-ray radiation. Many such scatterings take place even in a thin foil, so that the energy loss can be regarded as 'continuous':

$$\frac{dE}{dx} = -u(E) \quad (9)$$

where $u(E)$ is a function of particle energy depending on the shielding material. The coordinate x is measured along the particle path, which is not straight (due to the scatterings). The 'mean residual range' for an electron with initial energy E_0 is defined as the total path length required to reduce the energy to zero, viz.

$$r_0 = \int_0^{E_0} u(E)^{-1} dE \quad (10)$$

The mean residual range can be taken as a conservative estimate of the thickness of shielding required to eliminate all electrons below a certain energy E_0 . (The actual penetration depth is smaller due to the non-zero scattering angles. It is also less for isotropic impacts than for a collimated electron beam normal to the shield.) Table 4 shows the mean residual range of electrons in Al, computed according to Ref. 3. Tables of actual penetration depths should be available in the literature.

TABLE 4. Mean residual range of e^- in Al (Ref. 3).

E [MeV]	r_0 [mm]
.1	.07
.2	.22
.3	.40
.4	.61
.5	.84
.6	1.07
.7	1.31
.8	1.55
.9	1.80
1.0	2.05
1.5	3.29
2.0	4.51
2.5	5.71
3.0	6.89
3.5	8.06
4.0	9.20
4.5	10.33
5.0	11.44
5.5	12.54
6.0	13.63
6.5	14.71
7.0	15.78
7.5	16.84
8.0	17.89
8.5	18.94
9.0	19.98
9.5	21.01
10.0	22.03

To estimate the required shielding, we may proceed as follows. The total mean cross-section of the SM relay optics is about 30 cm^2 (averaged in all directions). If not more than $1 \text{ electron s}^{-1}$ is allowed (above the critical $E = 0.17 \text{ MeV}$), the maximum omnidirectional flux is about $1.0 \cdot 10^6 \text{ electrons cm}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$. According to Figure 6.1.4.5 (a) in the System Requirements, such a flux is obtained for $E_0 > 10 \text{ MeV}$ (extrapolation). According to Table 4 this in turn requires about 22 mm Al (or equivalently about 6 g cm^{-2} of shielding material). This is probably a rather conservative estimate, as the penetration depth for non-collimated electrons should be 20 to 30% smaller.

For the IDT tube and detector, a similar calculation indicates that all electrons below $E_0 \approx 5.5 \text{ MeV}$ should be blocked, which requires about 12 mm Al according to Table 4 (3 g cm^{-2}).

The required shielding in [g cm^{-2}] should be interpreted as the integrated column density along any straight line from the optical parts to the outside of the satellite.

References

1. Methods of Experimental Physics, Volume 12: Astrophysics (Part A)
Ed. N. Carleton, Academic Press 1974 (Ch. 1.4.2.1.2 and 7.3.1)
2. E21.HIP.00767 issue 4 (1983 June 15)
3. Berger, M.J., in Methods in Computational Physics, Volume 1, p 135